

Table 1. Minimum, maximum, and median values (mm) of the variables included in the QBA for stockpersons and calves across the 26 farms.

QBA descriptors	Min	Max	Median
Active	50	140	105
Relaxed	30	150	90
Uncomfortable	10	110	30
Calm	20	130	80
Content	40	140	90
Tense	20	110	50
Enjoying	30	130	95
Indifferent	20	120	65
Frustrated	10	90	45
Friendly	30	140	100
Bored	20	130	60
Positively occupied	30	140	100
Inquisitive	30	120	70
Irritable	20	110	50
Nervous	20	110	50
Boisterous	20	130	55
Uneasy	20	110	65
Sociable	40	140	100
Happy	40	140	100
Distressed	10	80	50
Calves			
Active	60	150	110
Relaxed	50	130	90

Uncomfortable	20	110	50
Calm	50	140	85
Content	70	150	100
Tense	20	150	70
Enjoying	50	150	105
Indifferent	20	130	60
Frustrated	20	150	60
Friendly	50	150	110
Bored	20	110	40
Positively occupied	50	150	105
Inquisitive	30	150	90
Irritable	20	110	55
Nervous	10	110	40
Boisterous	20	120	50
Uneasy	20	110	60
Sociable	40	140	100
Happy	80	140	110
Distressed	20	100	55

Legend: The QBA adjectives were pre-aggregated using the weights and calculation rules defined in the Welfare Quality® protocol for cattle (2009). Unlike the other scores, this is not a percentage value but a weighted sum of the individual scores of the adjectives, which can range from 0 to 150 mm.